

EVALUATION OF *INVITRO* ANTIDIABETIC ACTIVITY OF SOME NOVEL SYNTHESIZED 2(5'- SUBSTITUTED PHENYL 1', 3', 4' OXADIAZOL-2'-YL) AMINO-6-FLUORO-7-SUBSTITUTED (1, 3)-BENZOTHIAZOLES DERIVATIVES

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ABSTRACT

Benzothiazole is a unique bicyclic ring system. The benzothiazole nucleus has a number of pharmacological effects, including antibacterial, analgesic, anticonvulsant, hypoglycemic, and anti-inflammatory activity. Oxadiazoles are recognized as a promising group of bioactive heterocycles. So, it is recognized as an important building block in the drug discovery and development process. According to a review of the literature, 1, 3, 4-oxadiazole is an important moiety for the development of new drugs among heterocyclic compounds. Compounds containing the 1,3,4-oxadiazole moiety have been shown to have a wide range of biological effects, including anticancer, antibacterial, antifungal, antihypertensive, antiviral, anti-HIV, and hypoglycemic properties. Anti-diabetic activity was assessed utilizing alpha-amylase inhibitory activity, with Acarbose as a standard reference. The absorbance was measured at 565 nm wavelength. The current study intends to examine the *in-vitro* alpha amylase inhibitory activity of several novel produced 2(5'-substituted phenyl 1', 3', 4' oxadiazol-2'-yl) amino-6-fluoro-7-substituted (1,3)-

benzothiazole derivatives. The amylase inhibitory activity of the produced fluoro substituted benzothiazoles and oxadiazole derivatives B3, C3, F3, and V3 was investigated. In the alpha-amylase inhibition assay, a concentration of 7000 µg/ml resulted in maximal inhibition. As a result, our data suggest that B3, C3, and V3 may emerge as candidate molecules for anti-diabetic medicines, similar to the Acarbose effect.

KEYWORDS: Benzothiazole, 1, 3, 4-oxadiazole, Anti-diabetic, alpha-amylase.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a serious metabolic illness characterized by excessive blood glucose levels, impaired insulin action, or both. It is classified into several subtypes, including type-1, type-2, gestational diabetes, and others. Type 1 diabetes is caused by the autoimmune death of pancreatic β cells via T-cell-mediated inflammation and humoral response. Type 2 diabetes can range from major insulin shortage to a secretory malfunction accompanied by insulin resistance. Chronic hyperglycemia caused by diabetes is linked to long-term microvascular problems affecting the eyes, kidneys, and nerves, as well as an increased risk of cardiovascular disease. Diabetes medications include sulphonylureas (Tolbutamide and Glibenclamide), biguanides (Metformin), thiazolidinediones (Pioglitazone), meglitinide derivatives (Repaglinide and Nateglinide), α -glucosidase inhibitors (Acarbose and Voglibose), and DPP-4 inhibitors (Sitagliptin).^[1]

Alpha-amylase is a digestive enzyme that hydrolyses polysaccharides, including starch, into glucose and maltose; alpha-amylase inhibitors modulate blood glucose levels after meals; therefore, potential alpha-amylase inhibitors could be used as chemotherapeutic agents to treat diabetes. Acarbose, a mimic that inhibits the enzymes alpha-amylase, is the current treatment for type-2 diabetes; however, alpha-amylase inhibitors have been found to have a wide range of biological activities, in contrast to antidiabetic medications like acarbose, miglitol, celgosivir, 1-deoxynojirimycin, and voglibose.^[2]

According to WHO estimates, the number of people with diabetes is expected to rise by 35%. Over 150 million people globally have diabetes at the moment, and by 2025, that number is probably going to rise to 300 million or more. According to statistical projections, India will have the highest number of diabetics worldwide in 2025, with 57 million people, up from 15 million in 1995.^[3]

A heterocyclic molecule with nitrogen, oxygen, and sulphur has a wide range of uses in medical chemistry. Benzothiazole is a special bicyclic ring system. The benzothiazole nucleus has a variety of biological effects, including antibacterial, analgesic, anti-convulsant, hypoglycemic, and anti-inflammatory properties.^[1] The oxadiazole drugs were the first effective chemotherapeutic agents used systematically to prevent and treat bacterial infections in humans. Benzothiazole compounds containing an oxadiazole group and others have been noted to exhibit several pharmacological activities that are significant in clinical contexts. Oxadiazole derivatives are recognized for their antimicrobial properties, as well as their anti-inflammatory, anthelmintic, and anticonvulsant activities.^[4]

According to a review of the literature, 1,3,4-oxadiazole is a crucial moiety for the creation of novel medications among heterocyclic compounds. Numerous biological actions, including as anticancer, antibacterial, antifungal, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anticonvulsant, antihypertensive, antiviral, anti-HIV, and hypoglycemic qualities, have been discovered in compounds with the 1,3,4-oxadiazole moiety. In pharmaceutical chemistry, 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles have also drawn attention as stand-ins for carboxamides, carboxylic acids, and esters. Oxadiazoles have significant biological potential due to their unique structure, which makes them crucial for molecular planning.^[5]

Consequently, new *in-vitro* antidiabetic activity is more effective and desirable, necessitating pharmacological screening for some produced 2(5'-substituted phenyl 1',3',4' oxadiazol-2'-yl) amino-6-fluoro-7-substituted (1,3)-benzothiazoles derivatives. Therefore, using the alpha-amylase inhibition assay, the current work evaluates the oxadiazole and benzothiazole derivatives *in-vitro* antidiabetic effectiveness.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the synthesis of various 2(5'-substituted phenyl 1',3',4' oxadiazol-2'-yl) amino-6-fluoro-7-substituted (1,3)-benzothiazoles, the compound one was condensed with hydrazine hydrate in the presence of ethanol, yielding the substituted semi carbazide. Additionally, in the presence of ethanol, it refluxes with several substituted aromatic aldehydes.^[6-15]

Schiff basis of (1,3) benzothiazoles 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2-semicarbazides

2.6 gm of 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2-semicarbazide (1,3) benzothiazole was dissolved in 100% alcohol (12.6 ml), followed by the addition of vanillin, benzaldehyde, or cinnamaldehyde (0.015 mol). The aforementioned reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 hours, and the surplus

solvent was extracted under reduced pressure, yielding Schiff bases of (1,3) benzothiazole 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2 semi carbazides, which were recrystallised from alcohol.

Synthesis of 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2(5'-substituted phenyl) 1', 3', 4'oxadiazol-2'-yl amino (1,3) benzothiazoles

5.2-gram (0.00132 mol) Schiff bases of (1,3) benzothiazoles 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2-semi carbazides were mixed in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and a FeCl₃ solution was added while stirring constantly. The reaction mixture was agitated for 1 hour, then diluted with 100 cc of water and stored at room temperature for 48 hours. The separated product was filtered, washed with water, dried, and recrystallized from alcohol to get 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2(5'-substituted phenyl) 1', 3', 4'oxadiazol-2'-yl amino) (1,3) benzothiazoles.

Synthesis of 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2(5'-substituted phenyl) 1', 3', 4'oxadiazol-2'-yl amino (1,3) benzothiazoles

To 0.007 mol of 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2(5'-substituted phenyl) 1', 3',4'oxadiazol-2'-yl amino) (1,3). benzothiazoles was treated with equimolar quantity (0.0075 mol) of various substituted aromatic amines, PABA, morpholine, piperazine, p-toluidine, diphenylamine and n-Methyl piperazine were refluxed for 2 hrs. in the presence of DMF (dimethyl formamide) then the mixture was cooled and poured in to the crushed ice. The solid isolated was filtered, dried, and recrystallized from benzene and pure alcohol, yielding a variety of 2(5'-substituted phenyl) 1', 3', 4' oxadiazol-2'-yl amino)-6-fluoro-7-substituted (1,3)-benzothiazoles. Compounds B3, C3, F3, and V3 were synthesized and tested for anti-diabetic efficacy *in-vitro*.

SCHEME FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF 2(5'- SUBSTITUTED PHENYL 1', 3', 4' OXADIAZOL-2'-YL) AMINO-6-FLUORO-7-SUBSTITUTED (1, 3)-BENZOTHIAZOLES DERIVATIVES^[4]

Table 1: List of compounds procured.

B3	<p>2[5'-phenyl-1',3',4'-oxadiazol-2'-yl amino]-6-fluoro-7-p-nitro anilino (1,3)-benzothiazole</p>
C3	<p>3',4'-oxadiazol-2'-yl amino]-6-fluoro-7-p-nitro anilino (1,3)-benzothiazole</p>
F ₃	<p>6-fluoro-7-p-nitro anilino -2N-(5'-furyl 1',3',4' oxadiazol-2'-yl) 2N-(p-acetamido benzene sulphonamido)-(1,3)-benzothiazole</p>
V ₃	<p>2[5'-(o-hydroxy p-methoxy phenyl)-1',3',4'-oxadiazol-2'-yl amino]-6-fluoro-7-p-nitro anilino (1,3)-benzothiazole</p>

In-vitro* Anti-Diabetic activity*Alpha-amylase enzyme inhibition assay**

Clinical significance: Enzymes are made by animals, plants, and microorganisms. Microbial enzymes are particularly important since they are both cost-effective and stable. Amylase is one of the most widely used microbial enzymes.^[16] Alpha-amylase, which is found mostly in saliva and the pancreas, aids in the chemical breakdown of carbohydrates by hydrolyzing glycosidic linkages in starch and comparable substrate polysaccharides, converting them into oligosaccharides and simple absorbable sugars. While the salivary glands create salivary amylase and commence carbohydrate digestion in the mouth, the pancreas secretes a significant amount of pancreatic amylase into the duodenum to complete the digestion of incoming starch.^[17] Starch is a non-aromatic, white, granular polysaccharide made up of amylose (20-30%) and branching amylopectin (70-80%), with a trace of phosphate and lipids.^[18]

Acarbose is the most commonly utilized inhibitor of enzyme activity. These inhibitors slow glucose absorption, allowing hyperglycemic people to keep their glucose levels stable. However, the use of inhibitors is associated with some side effects, including diarrhoea and other digestive disorders. To minimize negative effects, natural α -amylase inhibitors should be considered.^[19]

Method: Enzymatic method of α -amylase. Spectrophotometric stop reaction

Principle

Assay procedure

A modified starch iodine procedure was used to conduct this investigation.^[20] To put it briefly, 1 millilitre of fluoro substituted benzothiazole derivatives or a standard with varying concentrations (0.5–3.5 mg/ml) was placed in test tubes that had already been labelled.

Each test tube received 20 μL of alpha-amylase and was incubated at 37°C for 10 minutes. After incubation, 200 μL of 1% starch solution was added to each test tube and the mixture was re-incubated for 1 hour at 37°C. Each test tube received 200 μL of 1% iodine solution, followed by 10 mL of distilled water. Absorbance of the combination was measured at 565 nm. The sample, substrate, and alpha-amylase blank were tested under the identical conditions. Each experiment was carried out in triplicate. The IC₅₀ value was derived using regression analysis.^[21]

$$\text{Inhibition of alpha- Amylase (\%)} = \frac{\text{Abs sample} - \text{Abs control}}{\text{Abs sample}} \times 100$$

Where, Abs control is the absorbance of the control reaction (containing all reagents except the test sample) and Abs sample is the absorbance of the test sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present study, the inhibitory activity of 2(5'-substituted phenyl) 1', 3', 4' oxadiazol-2'-yl amino)-6-fluoro-7-substituted (1,3)-benzothiazole derivatives was investigated and the results are given below. The *in-vitro* alpha amylase inhibitory activity of B3, C3 and V3 compounds exhibited significant antidiabetic activity.

Table 2: Effect of substituted benzothiazoles and oxadiazoles derivatives on *in-vitro* alpha amylase inhibition assay.

Concentration (mg/ml)	Standard (Acarbose)	% of inhibition of B3 compound	% of inhibition of C3 compound	% of inhibition of F3 compound	% of inhibition of V3 compound
1	15.73**	11.76	16.19	5.71	30.76
2	20.43	15.68	36.19	10.47	50
3	25.70**	18.62	53.33*	11.42	76.92**
4	32.70	31.37	67.61**	18.09	115.38***
5	42.46***	40.19	80**	10.47	142.30***
6	53.66***	46.07	89.52***	13.33	161.53***
7	68.36***	54.90**	107.61***	19.04	182.69***

Values are Mean S.E.M; n=7 *P< 0.05 **P< 0.01 and ***P < 0.001 vs Normal control

Fig. 1: Alpha-amylase inhibition of benzothiazoles and oxadiazoles derivatives at various concentrations.

The percentage of inhibition ranging from 1-7 mg/ml concentration of 2(5'-substituted phenyl) 1', 3', 4' oxadiazol-2'-yl amino)-6-fluoro-7-substituted (1,3)-benzothiazole derivatives shows concentration dependent table 2 and fig 1. The results revealed that B3, C3 and V3 compounds at a concentration of 7mg/ml showed a maximum percent inhibition 54.90, 107.61 and 182.69 respectively whereas in standard acarbose 78.40. The IC₅₀ value of B3, C3 and V3 compounds were found as **6.64**, **2.95** and **1.85 mg/ml**, whereas standard (acarbose) was found **6.43 mg/ml**.

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is possibly the world's fastest growing metabolic disorder. It is one of the most important health problems worldwide, indicating high prevalence and mortality. Management of diabetes without any side effects is still a challenge to medical communities.^[22]

Diabetes is prone to many complications due to the nature of the disease. Long-standing diabetes can lead to heart, kidney and circulation problems including stroke. Alpha amylase is an enzyme that hydrolyses alpha-bonds of large alpha linked polysaccharide such as glycogen and starch yield glucose and maltose. Alpha amylase inhibitors bind to alpha-bond of polysaccharide and prevent breakdown of polysaccharide into mono and disaccharide. The pancreatic and intestinal glucosidases are the key enzymes of dietary carbohydrate digestion and inhibitors of these enzymes may be effective in retarding glucose adsorption. This is because only monosaccharides are readily taken up from the intestine and all other carbohydrates have to be broken-down enzymatically before they can be absorbed. This breakdown occurs due to two major enzymes: amylase and Glucosidase. Alpha-amylase inhibitor indicates that it reduces the rate of absorption of carbohydrates, thereby reducing the Glycemic Index of foods.^[23,24]

The two most pronounced variations of diabetes are Type 1 diabetes mellitus and Type 2 diabetes mellitus both of which result in a hyperglycemic state. Type 1 diabetes mellitus is an autoimmune illness typified by the demolition of pancreatic b cells followed by dreadful insulin scarcity. On the other hand, Type 2 diabetes mellitus is more familiar and a major portion of diabetic patients (90 to 95%) are suffering from this dysfunction, which is categorized by peripheral insulin resistance and anomalies in the secretion of insulin.^[25] However, it is a non-communicable illness, experts are warning us about a figure of almost 438 million diabetic patients in 2030^[26] which considers the dreadfulness of this disease. In a broader sense, the causative factors of diabetes can reside in insulin resistance, abnormal insulin secretion and hepatic glucose synthesis along with impaired fat metabolism. Insulin resistance refers to the state where the efficacy of the insulin on target tissues becomes compromised particularly on adipocytes, hepatocytes and skeletal muscles^[27] which leads to hyperglycemia by impairing utilization of glucose and increasing hepatic glucose output.^[28]

Our present research suggests that, the potentially important role in managing diabetes via the inhibition of α -amylase enzyme activity. The α -amylase inhibitory activity of 2(5'-substituted phenyl) 1', 3', 4' oxadiazol-2'-yl amino)-6-fluoro-7-substituted (1,3)-benzothiazole derivatives was confirmed in this study.

The different dose concentration of 2(5'-substituted phenyl) 1', 3', 4' oxadiazol-2'-yl amino)-6-fluoro-7-substituted (1,3)-benzothiazole derivatives shows significant inhibition of α -amylase concentration of 1000-7000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, B3, C3 and V3 compounds showed more

significant *invitro* anti-diabetic activity, when compared to standard. Since, 2(5'-substituted phenyl) 1', 3', 4' oxadiazol-2'-yl amino)-6-fluoro-7-substituted (1,3)-benzothiazole derivatives exhibited a strong inhibition against alpha amylase it can be concluded that it has a great antidiabetic potential.

CONCLUSION

Researchers are becoming more interested in finding alpha amylase inhibitors that are safer and more effective from medicinal plants, herbs, anti-diabetic foods, and synthetic chemical compounds. In this present work, we showed that 2(5'- substituted phenyl 1', 3', 4' oxadiazol-2'-yl) amino-6-fluoro-7-substituted (1, 3)-benzothiazoles derivatives have α -amylase inhibitory action *in-vitro*. Our study concludes that chemicals B3, C3, and V3 were useful medications for treating diabetes and inhibiting the alpha amylase enzyme. To clarify the precise mode of action of 2(5'- substituted phenyl 1', 3', 4' oxadiazol-2'-yl) amino-6-fluoro-7-substituted (1, 3)-benzothiazoles derivatives as possible anti-diabetic medications, more research may be suggested about acute toxicity and *in-vivo* anti-diabetic efficacy.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare there is no conflict of interest.

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